

Electronic Supplementary Information

Two new Cu-based phosphonate Metal-Organic Frameworks as efficient water splitting photocatalysts.

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Synthesis of the Py(PO₃H₂)₄ linker

The lab-made Py(PO₃H₂) linker was synthesized following the Scheme S1:

Scheme S1. Synthetic route towards the preparation of Py(PO₃H₂)₄.

Py(Br)₄:

Py(Br)₄ was synthesized according to a published work with slight modifications.[1] In a 250 mL round-bottom flask, 2 g (9.88 mmol) of pyrene were dissolved in 60 mL of nitrobenzene at room temperature under constant magnetic stirring. 6.48 g of Br₂ (40.56 mmol) were added, and the resulting mixture was heated with a condenser at 120 °C for 5 h. After cooling to ambient temperature, acetone is added (approximately 50 mL) and the resulting yellowish Py(Br)₄ solid was filtered, washed with acetone and dried at ambient conditions. Yield = 97%.

Py(PO₃Et₂)₄:

In a 30 mL microwave reactor, 0.6 g of Py(Br)₄ (1.16 mmol), 0.1063 g of [Pd(PPh₃)₄] (8% based on the mol of Py(Br)₄, 0.092 mmol) and 6 mL of triethyl phosphite were added and stirred for 1 min. Then, the mixture was put inside the microwave and heated following the next temperature program: i) heating up to 200 °C during 5 min; ii) keeping at 200 °C for 25 min; and iii) cooling down to 60 °C.

After the reaction, the reactor was placed overnight at ambient conditions, leading to the crystallization of the desired compound. The reactor was filled with n-hexane, sonicated for 1 min and the resulting yellow solid was filtered. The obtained powder, denoted Py(PO₃Et₂)₄, was washed again by suspending

it in 30 mL of petroleum ether and sonicated for few minutes in order to remove some residual triethyl phosphite and impurities. Finally, was filtered and dried at ambient conditions. Yield = 92%.

***Py(PO₃H₂)₄*:**

Finally, 1.43 g (1.92 mmol) of Py(PO₃Et₂)₄ and 80 mL of HCl 12 M were mixed and heated at reflux temperature in a 250 mL round-bottom flask for 24 h. The resulting solid was filtered and washed with a small amount of acetone. The obtained yellowish compound, termed as Py(PO₃H₂)₄, was then dried at 60 °C. Yield = 98%.

Synthesis of [Ni₂(H₄L)(H₂O)₄]_n, (Ni-Pyrene P-MOF):

The synthesis of the nickel-pyrene based MOF was carried out based on a modified reported protocol.[2] 0.262 g (0.90 mmol) of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and 0.235 g (0.45 mmol) of the home-made linker Py(PO₃H₂)₄ were dispersed in 30 mL of a mixture of distilled water and MeOH (volumetric ratio 1:2) inside a 45 mL Teflon-lined autoclave. The reactor was closed and heated at 120 °C from RT in 6 h and then, maintained at this temperature for 48 h. After cooling to RT during 6 h, the obtained lime-green crystals were washed with water and methanol, recovered and dried under air. Yield: 70%

FTIR showed a significant shift of the phosphonate bands (ν P=O and ν P-O) of IEF-8, IEF-9 and Ni-Pyrene P-MOF when compared with the free linker (from 1006 to 1017 cm⁻¹, from 1076 to 1091 cm⁻¹ and from 1132 to 1123 cm⁻¹ for the IEF-8; from 1009 to 1017 cm⁻¹ and from 1068 to 1091 cm⁻¹ for the IEF-9; and from 1025 to 1032 cm⁻¹ and from 1097 to 1134 cm⁻¹ for the Ni-Pyrene P-MOF; Figs. S7, S8 and S16 respectively), supporting the coordination of the phosphonate groups to the metal (Cu and Ni respectively). Note here that the comparison of the IEF-9 was made with the tetra acid phosphonic linker and not with the ester analogue used during the synthesis due to the presence of fully deprotected linkers in the IEF-9 structure.

XPS spectra of the IEF-8 showed that, in the C 1s spectrum, the presence of the C-C sp² (284.4 eV) was confirmed, accompanied by the C-P (287 eV). In addition, the broad O 1s signal centred about 531.5 eV due to the presence of oxygen atoms in the -PO³⁻ functional group and in the Cu-O metal node can be identified. The P 2p spectrum shows a band centred at 133 eV attributable to the -PO³⁻ functional group. The Cu 2p spectrum shows the characteristic double peaks centred at 935 and 955 eV corresponding to the Cu²⁺ 2p^{3/2} and Cu²⁺ 2p^{1/2}, respectively.[3]

Stability tests carried out at room temperature were by suspending 20 mg of IEF-8 or IEF-9 in 20 mL of the selected organic solvents (final concentration 1 mg·mL⁻¹). The suspended solids were kept in sealed vials under stirring for 16 h. Then, the samples were collected by filtration.

In case of Ni-Pyrene P-MOF, the stability test was carried out at room temperature by suspending 20 mg of the compound in 4 mL of the selected organic solvents (final concentration 5 mg·mL⁻¹) and keeping it in sealed vials under stirring at 400 rpm for 24 h. After that, the samples were collected by centrifugation.

Figure S1: SEM image of IEF-8.

Table S1. Summary of relevant crystallographic information of IEF-8.

Chemical formula	$C_{16}H_{18}Cu_2O_{17}P_4$
M_r	733.28
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, $C2/c$
a, b, c (Å)	23.3876(6), 8.9957(2), 15.2771(4)
α, β, γ	90, 128.226(3), 90
V (Å ³)	2524.93(14)
Z	4
ρ_{calc} (g cm ⁻³)	1.929
$\mu_{\text{CuK}\alpha}$ (mm ⁻¹)	5.240
$F(000)$	1472
Crystal size (mm)	0.07x0.07x0.15
$T_{\text{min}}, T_{\text{max}}$	0.5987, 0.7536
Data collection temperature (K)	296
Radiation, λ (Å)	CuK α , 1.54178
$\theta_{\text{min}}, \theta_{\text{max}}$ (°)	5.47, 72.4
$h_{\text{min}}, h_{\text{max}}$	-28, 28
$k_{\text{min}}, k_{\text{max}}$	-11, 11
$l_{\text{min}}, l_{\text{max}}$	-18, 18

No. of measured, unique and observed [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$] reflections	11789, 11789, 9576
R_{int}	0.0479
No. of reflections, No. of parameters, no. of Restraints	11789, 204, 6
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)]$, $wR(F^2)$, S	0.0432, 0.1096, 1.024
ρ_{min} , ρ_{max} ($\text{e} \text{ \AA}^{-3}$)	-0.670, 0.639

Figure S2. Secondary building unit (SBU) of IEF-8.

Figure S3. SEM image of IEF-9.

Table S2. Summary of relevant crystallographic information of IEF-9.

Chemical formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ Cu ₂ O ₁₇ P ₄
<i>M_r</i>	735.28
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, <i>C2/c</i>
<i>a, b, c</i> (Å)	16.2265(12), 22.2273(17), 7.4562(6)
<i>α, β, γ</i>	90, 117.080(3), 90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2394.4(7)
Z	4
<i>ρ_{calc}</i> (g cm ⁻³)	2.040
<i>μ_{MoKa}</i> (mm ⁻¹)	2.130
<i>F</i> (000)	1480
Crystal size (mm)	0.12×0.1×0.1
<i>T_{min}, T_{max}</i>	0.052154, 0.094897
Data collection temperature (K)	296
Radiation, λ (Å)	MoKa, 0.7107354178
<i>θ_{min}, θ_{max}</i> (°)	3.089, 27.521
<i>h_{min}, h_{max}</i>	-21,18
<i>k_{min}, k_{max}</i>	0,28
<i>l_{min}, l_{max}</i>	0,9
No. of measured, unique and observed [I ≥ 2σ(I)] reflections	2759, 2759, 2635
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.0370
No. of reflections, No. of parameters, No. of restraints	2759, 184, 0
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.0405, 0.1034, 1.179
<i>ρ_{min}, ρ_{max}</i> (e Å ⁻³)	-0.664, 0.652

Figure S4. SBU of IEF-9.

Figure S5. Linker stacking of IEF-9 along the c axis.

Figure S6. Le Bail profile fitting of the IEF-8.

Table S3. Structural parameters of IEF-8 obtained by SC-XRD and by Le Bail refinement.

	SC-XRD	PXRD
Space Group	<i>C2/c</i>	<i>C2/c</i>
a (Å)	23.39	23.45
b (Å)	8.99	9.00
c (Å)	15.28	15.32
α (°)	90	90
β (°)	128.22	128.37
γ (°)	90	90

Figure S7. Le Bail profile fitting of the IEF-9.

Table S4. Structural parameters of IEF-9 obtained by SC-XRD and by Le Bail refinement.

	SC-XRD	PXRD
Space Group	<i>C2/c</i>	<i>C2/c</i>
a (Å)	16.13	16.34
b (Å)	22.28	22.24
c (Å)	7.42	7.45
α (°)	90	90
β (°)	117.36	117.91
γ (°)	90	90

Figure S8. FTIR spectra of the IEF-8 (blue) and Py(PO₃H₂)₄ linker (black).

Figure S9. FTIR spectra of the IEF-9 (green) and Py(PO₃H₂)₄ linker (black).

Figure S10. TGA curve of the IEF-8 under air.

Figure S11. VT-PXRD of the IEF-8 under air.

Figure S12. TGA curve of the IEF-9 under air.

Figure S13. VT-PXRD of the IEF-9 under air.

Figure S14. IEF-8 PXRD patterns after stability test.

Figure S15. IEF-9 PXRD patterns after stability test.

Figure S16. IEF-8 PXRD patterns after stability test in different RH atmospheres.

Figure S17. IEF-9 PXRD patterns after stability test in different RH atmospheres.

Figure S18. SEM image of Ni-Pyrene P-MOF.

Figure S19. FTIR spectra of the Ni-Pyrene P-MOF (orange) and Py(PO₃H₂)₄ linker (black).

Figure S20. TGA curve of the Ni-Pyrene P-MOF under air. Weight losses up to 270 °C and from 270 °C to 365 °C correspond to the loss of 4 coordinated water molecules (8.68 wt.%) and 4 hydroxyl groups (10.04 wt.%) respectively.

Figure S21. VT-PXRD of the Ni-Pyrene P-MOF under air.

Figure S22. Ni-Pyrene P-MOF PXRD patterns after stability test.

Figure S23. High resolution XPS spectra of C 1s (a), O 1s (b), P 2p (c) and Cu 2p (d) of the IEF-8 solid.

Figure S24. High resolution XPS spectra of C 1s (a), O 1s (b), P 2p (c) and Cu 2p (d) of the IEF-9 solid.

Figure S25. High resolution XPS spectra of C 1s (a), O 1s (b), P 2p (c) and Ni 2p (d) of the Ni-Pyrene P-MOF solid.

Figure S26. UV-Vis diffuse spectra (a, c, e) and Tauc plots (b, d, f) with optical band gaps (E_g) of IEF-8 (a, b), IEF-9 (c, d) and Ni-Pyrene P-MOF (e, f).

Figure S27. XPS valence band for IEF-8 (a), IEF-9 (b) and Ni-Pyrene P-MOF (c)

Figure S28. Ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS) valence band for IEF-8

Figure S29. PXRD patterns of fresh (a) and used (b) of the IEF-8 (top), IEF-9 (middle) and Ni-Pyrene P-MOF (bottom) after the photocatalytic HER.

Figure S30. FTIR spectra of fresh (a) and used (b) IEF-8

Figure S31. EPR data (a) and a schematic representation of the photocatalytic HER reaction (b)

Table S5: Comparative table of several MOFs used in HER

Photocatalysts	Irradiation (lamp)	Sacrificial agents	H ₂ production rate ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)	Recycled times (Time per cycle-h)	General remarks	Reference
[Cu ₂ (Py(PO ₃ H) ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂] \cdot 4H ₂ O (IEF-8)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 150 W)	MeOH	81.8	4 (22 h)	The catalyst maintains its photocatalytic activity and structural integrity based on XRD and FT-IR at least during four consecutive reuses (88 h; 22 h/cycle). The production under simulated sunlight irradiation is 0.034 mmol g ⁻¹ after 22 h	This work
[Cu ₂ (Py(PO ₃ H) ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂] \cdot 3H ₂ O (IEF-9)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 150 W)	MeOH	33.6	– (22 h)		This work
[Ni ₂ (Py(PO ₃ H) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄ Ni Pyrene P-MOF	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 150 W)	MeOH	42.2	– (22 h)		This work
[Ti ₂ O ₃ (C ₄ O ₄)] (IEF-11)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 150 W)	MeOH	34.8	10 (22 h)		[1]
([Ni(H ₄ ttbmp)(H ₂ O) ₂] \cdot H ₂ O) (IEF-13)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 150 W)	MeOH	77	3 (22 h)	The photocatalyst deactivates gradually upon reuse (22 h/cycle) and after four uses the photocatalyst loses about 25 % of its initial activity	[2]
Ti ₈ O ₈ (OH) ₄ (BDC) ₆ (MIL-125)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp; 500 W)	MeOH	32	– (24 h)		[3]

$\text{Ti}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4[\text{BDC}]_6(\text{NH}_2)_6$ (<i>plasma treated</i> MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp, 150 W)	MeOH	34	- (22 h)	The use of as-prepared MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂ without a plasma treatment results in a production of about 16 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ after 22 h	[4]
$\text{Ti}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4[\text{BDC}]_6(\text{NH}_2)_6$ (MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂)	UV-Vis (Hg-Xe lamp, 150 W)	MeOH	37.5	- (22h)		This work
$\text{Ti}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4[\text{BDC}]_6(\text{NH}_2)_6$ (MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂)	Visible $\lambda > 400$ nm	AcN:TEOA	61	- (10 h)	The sample having the (110) facet exhibits the highest photocatalytic activity respect to analogous samples having other ones such as (001) or (100) ones.	[5]
$\text{Ti}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4[\text{BDC}]_6(\text{NH}_2)_6$ (MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂)	Visible $\lambda > 400$ nm (Xe lamp, 300 W)	$\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3:\text{Na}_2\text{S}$	0	- (4 h)		[6]
$\text{Ti}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_4[\text{BDC}]_6(\text{NH}_2)_6$ (MIL-125(Ti)-NH ₂)	Simulated sunlight (150 W, AM 1.5)	Glycerol	360	- (3 h)		[7]
$\text{Zr}_6(\mu_3\text{-O})_4(\mu_3\text{-OH})_4(\text{OH})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{FeTCPPCl})_2$ (PCN-222)	Simulated sunlight	MeOH	38	- (22 h)	The photocatalytic reusability under these reaction conditions has not been addressed	[8]
$\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{BDC})(\text{OH})$ (MIL-53(Al)-NH ₂)	UV-Vis (Xe lamp, 300 W)	MeOH	0	- (2.5 h)	The photocatalyst is inactive for the HER in the absence of Ni^{2+} as co-catalyst coordinated to the amino groups of the terephthalate organic ligand	[9]
$\text{Ti}(\text{DOBDC})_{1.5}(\text{Et}_2\text{MeNH})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (MIL-167)	UV (Xe/Hg lamp; 500 W)	$\text{CH}_3\text{CN}:\text{TEA}$	7.7 52	- (24 h)		[10]
$\text{TiO}_{0.5}(\text{DOBDC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (pipH ₂) _{0.5} ·H ₂ O	UV	$\text{CH}_3\text{CN}:\text{TEA}$	~0	- (24 h)		[10]

(MIL-169)	(Xe/Hg lamp; 500 W)					
Ti ₈ O ₈ (OH) ₄ (BDC) ₆ (MIL-125)	UV (Xe/Hg lamp; 500 W)	CH ₃ CN:TEA	52	- (24 h)		[10]
[Al ₃ (OH) ₃ (HTCS) ₂] (AITCS-1)	Visible (Xe lamp; 300 W)	TEOA	50	- (10 h)		[11]
Ru-TBP-Zn	Visible (solid state lamp, 230 W)	TEOA	0.24	6 (72 h)*		[12]
Ti(DOBDC) _{1.5} (Et ₂ MeNH) ₂ · nH ₂ O (MIL-167)	UV-Vis	TEA	7.7	-		[53]
Fe ₃ O(H ₂ O) ₂ OH(BTC) ₂ MIL-100(Fe)	λ > 400- 800 nm (Xe lamp, 300 W)	MeOH	5.9	- (3 h)		[13]
Cr ₃ O(OH)(H ₂ O) ₂ (BDC) ₃ MIL-101(Cr)	Visible (Xe lamp, 300 W)	Na ₂ S:Na ₂ SO ₃	0	- (2 h)		[14]
Zr ₆ O ₄ (OH) ₄ (BDC) ₆ (NH ₂) ₆ NH ₂ -UiO-66	λ > 400 nm (Xe lamp, 300 W)	Na ₂ S:Na ₂ SO ₃	0	- (5 h)		[15]

Py(PO₃H₂)₄ = 1,3,6,8-tetra(4-phosphonate)-1,3,5-triazine; C₄O₄H₂ = 3,4-Dihydroxy-3-cyclobutene-1,2-dione (squaric acid); H₆ttbmp = 4,6-bis[4-(phosphonomethyl)phenyl]-1,3,5-triazine; H₂BDC = terephthalic acid; H₄DOBDC = 2,5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid (terephthalic acid); H₄TCS = 3,3',3'',3'''-silanetetrayltetrakis-benzoic acid; bpy = 4,4'-bipyridine; TCPP = Tetrakis(4-carboxyphenyl)porphyrin; H₄TBP = 5,10,15,20-tetra(p-benzoato)porphyrin; TEA = triethylamine; TEOA = triethanolamine; H₃BTC = benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid (trimesic acid)

* Structural integrity of the compound after experiment not provide

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